

THE UMEI - UNIVERSAL MARKET ENABLING INTERFACE. ENABLING STANDARD INTERACTION WITH VARIOUS FLEXIBILITY MARKETS TO PROCURE GRID SERVICES

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ABSTRACT

The Universal Market Enabling Interface (UMEI), developed in the H2020 EUniversal Project and one of its major results, aims to support the transformation of the energy system into a new multi-energy and multi-consumer concept, guaranteeing a sustainable, secure, and stable electricity supply. It brings forward a universal, adaptable, and modular approach to interlink active system management from network operators with electricity markets and the provision of flexibility services. UMEI is provided as an open-source, universal, and distributed communication standard to overcome system-specific differences and hence to facilitate the interaction between DSOs, Flexibility Service Providers (FSPs), and Flexibility Market Operators (FMOs), without the need for a mediation platform. This interoperable interface was developed by multiple market actors (3 DSOs, 2 FMOs, and 1 FSP).

1. INTRODUCTION

The energy transition and the increasing electrification of the society pose a pressing challenge to improve the operation and planning of the distribution grid. The integration of renewable energy sources, particularly in a decentralized manner, requires new approaches to grid operation and planning. Additionally, the inclusion of prosumers in the system at residential and commercial levels creates volatile power flows that change the paradigm and may generate constraints in the grid. To address these challenges, Distribution System Operators (DSOs) will increasingly need to rely on new forms of market-based system services, such as local flexibility, to solve network congestion problems, voltage abnormalities, and other issues.

Flexibility for grid operation has been subject to research and attention of the sector for a long time as distribution networks are being challenged with the large-scale integration of distributed generation. Instead of coping

with this new paradigm in a passive way, DSOs and other players are taking the lead in building new mechanisms to leverage the new resources to manage the network in the most cost-efficient way.

Consumers and prosumers are key participants in this framework and will be able to identify new incentives to invest in local distributed resources. Also at the regulatory level, the consumers have an essential role in the management of the electricity system and foresees their participation in future flexibility markets [1]. More recently, ACER submitted the framework guidelines on demand response to the EC [2], which represents the starting of the process to develop a new network code to allow the uptake of flexibility by both DSOs and TSOs.

The enhanced integration of several actors, in turn, requires enhanced coordination mechanisms. The Universal Market-enabling Interface (UMEI) is intended to be a key component of these enhanced coordination schemes, by providing a communication channel for DSOs and FSPs to various flexibility markets, and between them, to unlock the available flexibility services at each specific location.

This article describes the work that led to the development and set-up of the UMEI as an interface to allow the interaction between system operators, flexibility market operators, and flexibility providers.

2. GRID FLEXIBILITY SERVICES

As the starting process for the development of the UMEI, a definition of grid flexibility services that are useful for DSOs was carried out in [3], in which an extensive characterisation of the needs and services of system operators was made.

Depending on the type of needs for a certain situation, a harmonized set of market services may be used by the system operator. This work led to the conclusion that flexibility at the distribution level may be used to deal with the needs referred to in Table I.

Table I - Flexibility Needs and Services

Needs	Flexibility Service
Physical congestion	- Corrective and Predictive Congestion Management
Control of voltage violation	- Corrective and Predictive Voltage Control
Support to network planning	- Support to Network Planning
Phase balancing	- Corrective and Predictive Voltage Control
Support to planned and unplanned operations	- Corrective and Predictive Congestion Management - Corrective and Predictive Voltage Control - Islanding - Emergency Load Control - Mobile Generation Capacity
Support to extreme events	- Corrective and Predictive Congestion Management - Corrective and Predictive Voltage Control - Emergency Load Control - Islanding - Black Start - Mobile Generation Capacity
Support to islanding	- Islanding

This identification and characterization set the basis for the subsequent development of use cases for three large-scale pilots in the project, and for the test implementation in real scenarios with end consumers of some of these flexibility services, with a market-based approach.

3. THE UMEI

The UMEI has been developed having as basis an agnostic, adaptable, and modular architectural design that implements a combination of different APIs to link DSOs and market parties (FSPs) with flexibility market platforms, as illustrated in Figure 1. This approach allows for end-to-end data exchange between multiple DSOs, FMOs, and FSPs in a common way, without specific setups for each one of the parties.

The UMEI architecture was developed according to the identified market-based procurement processes identified on both flexibility market platforms, and on the required flexibility services for the DSO, to support the following market stages:

- Needs assessment
- Procurement/trading
- Activation
- Measurement data exchange

Figure 1 - Reference Architecture

The high-level process used for the development of the UMEI is depicted in Figure 2, and the development began with the examination of the flexibility services and the corresponding market products, identified through the analysis of business and system use cases for the three demonstrations of the EUniversal project.

Figure 2 - UMEI Development Scheme

The result is a set of open REST APIs, organized into 7 functional groups, which follow the chronological and functional order of market operations during the pre-trading, trading, and post-trading phases. The modular approach of the UMEI allows for the adoption and implementation of the messages depending on the specific needs of each entity. For example, the meter data exchange process can be done bilaterally between the DSO, in its role as meter data operator, and the Flexibility Service Provider (FSP), which controls the resources.

The development of the interface has been a joint effort from the involved parties in EUniversal project, both FMOs (NODES and N-Side), FSP (CENTRICA), and three DSOs (E-REDES (Portugal), MITNETZ STROM (Germany), and ENERGA OPERATOR (Poland)).

As the UMEI is designed to be distributed, it does not define central registries, databases, or instances of

applications. This means that all data exchanged through the UMEI must be kept at the origin and/or destination, and each party is responsible for ensuring the proper handling of the data.

To successfully implement the UMEI, NODES, and N-SIDE, as FMOs, had to reconcile their differing approaches, which were based on their respective background, experience, and reference pilot projects. This required finding a balance between creating a standard that covered the relevant functions of each phase of flexibility market operations and ensuring that each market platform functioned correctly individually.

To tackle this objective, NODES and N-SIDE aligned on the list of data model fields for the different resources of the UMEI, such as the orders, portfolios, etc. The discussions concerned the presence of specific payload data, as well as their designation, types, and descriptions. Part of the data structures was set as optional as all FMOs may not support them, but N-SIDE and NODES still agreed on their relevance, applying redundancy mechanisms to the UMEI, which allows for other parties to choose what best fits the purpose for its usage.

A GitHub repository was created to iterate issues and pull requests, accordingly. The systematic validation process of the pull/change requests by experts from both NODES and N-SIDE triggered multi-lateral discussions and agreements which led to a harmonized vision in the design of the UMEI specification. OpenAPI [https://www.openapis.org] was used as the definition language. This is the most common and well-supported way of defining APIs accessible using the standard web technologies of today – JSON over HTTP.

Structure

The UMEI is composed of a set of APIs, available at <https://euniversal.eu/the-umei/>, and is organized into several functional groups that allow market participants to retrieve and send information to each other.

The API interface is divided into several functional groups, as detailed in Table II. The division follows the natural chronological and functional order of market operations:

- Prequalification phase
- Pre-trading phase
 - Defining baselines, the expected power profile usage, for portfolios
 - Defining flexibility zones – the expected demand for flexibility
 - Extracting this information, along with market and portfolio information, for use in the next phase
- Trading phase
 - Posting orders, reading orders, and trades

- Post-trading phase
 - Providing meter readings for assets used in trades

Table II - UMEI structure

Process Group	Name	Usage
Baseline	Managing portfolio baselines	Used by the FSPs to manage baselines in the market platform.
Order	Manage Market Orders	Used by the DSOs and FSPs to view and execute orders' related operations in the market platform. The FMO will perform clearing/matching, either continuously or on a specific schedule, between orders. The result of this process will be the trades.
Meter Reading	Manage Meter Readings	Used by the DSOs, and possibly other market participants, to submit and manage metering data.
Market	List All Markets	Used by market participants to get the available markets.
Portfolio	Manage Portfolios	Used by FSPs to submit and manage portfolios on the market.
Trade	List Market Trades	Used by market participants to retrieve the market trades (the result of the matching process between buy/sell orders).
Flexibility Zones	Manage Flexibility Zones	Used by DSOs to define specific flexibility areas, composed of a set of portfolios.

Each group is composed of a set of APIs that allow for CRUD (Create, Read, Update and Delete) operations to be performed on the registered resources in the market platform. For instance, with the Order group it is possible to submit new buy and sell orders, coming from the FSP and DSO side, but also to fetch, eliminate and update orders already submitted before the clearing of the market occurs.

Guidelines for Implementation

The steps for the implementation of the UMEI are simple for anyone familiar with REST API implementation. The following steps are necessary:

- 1) Map the interactions for your flexibility-related process and the information to be exchanged
- 2) Identify the involved actors in the exchange of information
- 3) Identify which actor is going to provide and receive information upon request (reactively)
- 4) Check the UMEI list of available APIs and identify which one fits the purpose
- 5) The actor identified in 3. will be the one to host the chosen API (implement server-side code) and make it available for the other(s)

For the implementation, actors can leverage OpenAPI features enabled by Swagger [4] and generate client and server-side boilerplate code. The setup process for the implementation implies that there is the possibility to have more than one hosting actor for the system, and no need for a mediation platform, making the UMEI a truly distributed data exchange interface. Naturally, whoever party implements the API becomes responsible for managing and providing credentials to others. This makes the usage of the UMEI particularly straightforward for actors which act mostly as UMEI API clients (e.g., DSO and FSP) since they just need to invoke an API endpoint to send and retrieve information.

Table III - Process Mapping and API Selection

Step	Actors			UMEI Endpoint
	DSO	FMO	FSP	
Send flexibility orders to the market	X	X (API host)	X	POST /Orders
Retrieve market clearing results	X	X (API host)	X	GET /Trades
Create a new portfolio of flexible resources		X (API host)	X	POST /Portfolios
Periodically send meter readings to the FSP	X		X (API host)	POST /MeterReadings/create-multiple
Retrieve meter readings	X (API host)	X	X	GET /MeterReadings

It can be analysed, on the example from Table III, that almost all processes are hosted by the FMO, except for meter readings messages, which contain personal information from consumers (subject to GDPR) and therefore are only exchanged between the DSO and FSP. However, the referred process mapping and hosting actors may change depending on the specific scenario.

4. FIELD IMPLEMENTATIONS

The UMEI is currently being tested in the field by three pilots across Europe: Portugal, Germany, and Poland. The pilots are testing various flexibility services and products with the UMEI.

In the Portuguese pilot market-based long-term and short-term flexibility, services are tested for the MV and LV

grid. The UMEI is used to perform the harmonized data exchange between one DSO, two FMOs, and one FSP.

In the German pilot, congestion management using market-based procurement of flexibility in a LV grid via the UMEI and combined with the mandatory redispatch regime is tested.

And lastly in Poland, grid observability and the exploitation of the network flexibility, through DLR (Dynamic Line Rating) mechanisms are being tested to offer more line capacity to producers when needed.

The UMEI is thus proving its use and applicability for a wide range of products. Table IV shows the services and approaches that are being tested in the three pilots.

Table IV - Services being tested through the UMEI

Service	Buyer	Auction Type	Demo	Market Platform
Corrective Congestion Management and Voltage Control	DSO	Continuous Market	Germany; Poland	NODES
Corrective and Predictive Congestion management and voltage control	DSO	Continuous Market and Call Market	Portugal	NODES; N-SIDE
Corrective Congestion management and Corrective Voltage Control	DSO	Continuous Market and Call Market	Portugal	NODES; NSIDE
Corrective Congestion management via flexibility of the line capacity	Producer	Continuous Market	Poland	NODES

5. CONCLUSION

The UMEI consists of a set of OpenAPI specifications that allows for the exchange of information between System Operators, FMOs, and FSPs for the purpose of mobilisation and activation flexibility, without the need for a central platform or mediator system.

There are numerous advantages of using the UMEI for System Operators, FMOs, and FSPs, and ultimately for the consumer, who indirectly benefits from the use of the interface, by having potentially more opportunities to participate in flexibility provision arrangements. By using the UMEI, System Operators have a standard way of communicating with the market platforms and the flexibility providers, regardless of the underlying market platform. Current and new FMOs can adopt a field-tested interface to set up new markets and ease the integration process with other actors, facilitating the entrance into new markets and regions and communicating with any System

Operator or FSP. FSPs can interact with multiple markets using just one instantiation of the UMEI, with the only requirement being the correct endpoint parameters for each implementation. Furthermore, by using this interface, any actor can host the APIs by themselves without having to rely on a sole hosting party, making the process easier for any DSO to implement without a high level of complexity and effort. Ultimately, the UMEI allows the various parties to focus more on their business processes and reduce implementation costs.

At the time of writing this article, the UMEI is finalized and being tested in the EUniversal project field demonstrations in three European countries: Portugal, Germany, and Poland, for the market-based procurement of several system services such as congestion management in the MV and LV grid, voltage control, and dynamic line rating.

The UMEI is publicly available on GitHub [5] and is open to any interested parties to test and check the specifications, being set as an open-source component to enable the streamlined uptake of market-based flexibility. This way, all users can collaborate on maintenance and development work, which can be proposed by users or potential new users whenever new needs arise since all can collaborate on its evolution through GitHub.

Also in this work, further technical enhancements to the specification were identified, and can be seen as development opportunities for the future:

- Compatibility with TSO (e.g., for pre-qualification purposes)
- Inclusion of other flexibility process steps (e.g., financial settlement)
- Flexibility register synchronization
- Developing and distributing an official client library, in one or more languages
- Developing and distributing an official implementation validation test suite or set of tools

Some of these functionalities have already started being developed within the scope of other European research projects.

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